

The Effect Of Computerized Accounting Informtion System, Organization Culture And Firm Size Oncompanies Performance In Iraq Construction Companies

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 17, 2024</p> <p>Accepted: March 18, 2025</p> <p>Keywords : CAIS, Firm Size, Organization Culture, Construction Companies, Performance</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15049695</p>	<p><i>This study presents the scholarly basis for this study. It reviews literature on constrictions companies' performance, this study also presents the range of computerize accounting information system elements effect constrictions industry and their roles in building a modern constrictions company. The need for and the viability of implementing factors of computerize information system and organization culture, firm size-enabled in constrictions companies' performance is argued with highlights of the prospects and challenges of the implementation process. This research also introduces the methods used to collect data to see how computerized accounting information system, corporate culture and company size have affected the success of constricton businesses. The potential benefits and issues of CAIS, organization culture and firm size in constrictions companies' performance are presented to give an understanding for the need for a unified framework for CAIS implementation and performance in the constricton's companies. Outcome from this research will be a proposed framework for CAIS and performance for building System.</i></p>

Introduction

In many economies, Construction is an important aspect. A significant proportion of the gross domestic product is also contingent on construction. Civil engineering demonstrates the construction process and the architect's ideas and the detailed plans of the builder. The quality of construction work depends primarily on the cooperation of the project parties' efforts. The purpose of the construction team is to complete the project in accordance with specifications and customer requirements within the estimated cost, schedule time, no defects and. Building projects therefore require good management and successful approaches throughout the project life cycle(Cavka, Staub-French, & Poirier, 2017).The output of the construction industry is affected by national economies(Ma, Cai, Cai, & Dong, 2019).In a diverse world of constant and rapid changes, building organizations run. Therefore, to prevent survival problems, construction companies must adapt to this climate(Keenan, 2015).

Performance is an indicator of the progress of building projects; it can be calculated in terms of time, expense and efficiency(Eleftheriadis, Mumovic, & Greening, 2017).The success of construction projects is determined by the performance of unskilled employees, skilled workers and professional personnel(Alaghbari, Al-Sakkaf, & Sultan, 2019).The ultimate aim of stakeholders is to understand the standard instead of others when executing the construction project(Aarseth, Ahola, Aaltonen, Økland, & Andersen, 2017).The primary cause of construction project failure is failure and performance issues(Pärn, Edwards, & Sing, 2017).Owners, consultants, regulators, stakeholders, and contractors are the parties to the construction industry; a vast number of parties make up the complex life of the construction industry. Social objectives can be reached or improved through the construction industry, which is an engine for motivating economic growth. Weak construction output leads to unstable economic conditions and prevents the management of construction projects from adequately handling and recording construction concerns to be used as guides in the future(Irfan, Thaheem, Gabriel, Malik, & Nasir, 2019).As a measure of economic growth, infrastructure improvements, such as bridges, highways, and homes, can be used. As a result , the construction industry plays an important role in establishing and achieving social objectives.(Costin, Adibfar, Hu, & Chen, 2018).Project performance indicators are incorporated in construction projects within the expected expense, schedule period and according to specifications and customer requirements(M.-H. Kim, Lee, & Choi, 2018).As a consequence of the degree of complexities posed in procedures, budgets and technologies, the construction industry is an efficient framework(Greenhalgh et al., 2018).It is evident that several developing nations have programs to boost and track the performance of the construction industry at different stages of socio-economic growth(Liu, Yuan, Hafeez, & Yuan, 2018).In economic growth, the construction industry plays a critical role and provides a greater number of employees (Camacho et al., 2018). Organization Contextinclude Organization readiness and

Financial readiness and the last Environment context which include External pressure on the dependent variable which represent by constructions companies' performance. Since there are many previous studies that confirmed the positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables that we took in our study (Aldholay, Isaac, Abdullah, & Ramayah, 2018; Choi, Hwang, & Lee, 2017; Guenther & Heinicke, 2019; Isaac, Abdullah, Ramayah, Mutahar, & Alrajawy, 2018; Josefy, Kuban, Ireland, & Hitt, 2015; Y. Kim, Park, & Choi, 2017; Mikalef, Krogstie, Pappas, & Pavlou, 2020; Sun, Cegielski, Jia, & Hall, 2018).

Materials And Methods

How this research will be performed is shown in Figure 1. In this work, using a formal questionnaire and interview, both qualitative and quantitative methods will be used. Qualitative research approach was chosen in this research to identify CAIS and performance for Iraqi constructions companies which will require interview of respective stakeholders, especially in relationship with the component models that gravely lack empirical research studies, to create a corpus of data that will then be used in the development of the framework. For quantitative approach, questionnaire will be used for its evaluation. The proposed framework would specify the CAIS element, organization culture, firm size and performance administrative/managerial needs for the implementation of CAIS, organization culture, firm size and performance. The framework is to integrate all the component models and presents a unifying front for their implementation. This will also solve the observed practical problem associated with implementation of CAIS and Performance in the constructions industry.

Fig. 1: Key stages in the research process

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Theoretical framework building to examine

To build our framework we will take both organizational culture and government policy as the mediator. There are many studies that showed the effect of organizational culture on performance of contracting companies as an independent variable (Ahammad, Tarba, Liu, & Glaister, 2016; Altay, Gunasekaran, Dubey, & Childe, 2018; Naranjo-Valencia, Jiménez-Jiménez, & Sanz-Valle, 2016; Nazarian, Atkinson, & Foroudi, 2017; Pambreni, Khatibi, Azam, & Tham, 2019). So, we built a framework and took it as mediator to extract new results. We also took government policy as the second mediator to examine the effect on constructions companies' performance. Since many studies have also measured its effect as an independent variable on constructions company's performance (Brieger, Francoeur, Welzel, & Ben-Amar, 2019; Carson, Dunbar, Chenhall, & Bailie, 2020; Platt et al., 2018; Villalonga-Olives & Kawachi, 2017; Wang & Teo, 2020). We build our framework with firm size as moderator to make sure we will analyse pure result even when we take different size of companies.

Theoretical framework builds to examine

Figure 1. Theoretical framework

The relationship between CAIS and firm performance has been discussed in previous studies. (González-Rodríguez, Martín-Samper, Köseoglu, & Okumus, 2019; Ng & Kee, 2018; Torres, Sidorova, & Jones, 2018; Uzrail & Bardai, 2019). Based on the considerable findings of the previous studies that have highlighted the important but poor link between CAIS and firm performance (Ashrafi & Ravasan, 2018; Criado-Gomis, Iniesta-Bonillo, Cervera-Taulet, & Ribeiro-Soriano, 2020; González-Rodríguez et al., 2019; Tallon, Queiroz, Coltman, & Sharma, 2019), the current research took new one step further via taking in consideration the role of organizational culture as a mediating variable that explains the linkage between CMIS and constructions companies' performance. The majority of organizational culture studies treated culture as independent variable influencing companies' performance, or as dependent variable affected by some antecedent variables such as (de Holanda Rabelo et al., 2015; Paliszkievicz, Svanadze, & Jikia, 2017; Shao, 2019; Yusof, Said, & Ali, 2016). However, one of the most significant features of organizational culture is the mediating role that it plays in enhancing companies' performance (Al-Ali, Singh, Al-Nahyan, & Sohal, 2017; Alaarj, Abidin-Mohamed, & Bustamam, 2016; Basheer, Siam, Awn, & Hassan, 2019; Kalmuk & Acar, 2015; Yu & Choi, 2016). For example, Al-Ali, Singh, Al-Nahyan, & Sohal, (2017) argued that organizational culture is important and this importance stems because its impact as an essential mediating variable in determining the companies' performance.

Although several theoretical agreements on the mediation function of organizational culture, as the researcher's best information, there is no prior work that has evaluated the mediating role of organizational culture in the relationship between CAIS and the performance of contracting companies.

Problem and issues

One of the most diverse and complex manufacturing environments reflects the building industry. The construction sector forms a high percentage of the economy in developing countries like Iraq. Despite its great economic significance, as compared to other sectors, such as the oil or manufacturing sector, the construction industry consistently demonstrates lower productivity levels. This shows that the Iraqi economy has achieved impressive growth in its gross domestic product (GDP) over the past three decades. (Simon, 2019), But without expense, time, and efficiency, the construction industry has carried out magnificent projects effectively. (Al-Shammery, 2017; Al-Turfi, 2017; Radha, 2020). In addition, the construction industry has a poor perception of low productivity and efficiency. (Al-Abadi, Handhal, & Al-Ginamy, 2020; Al-Rubaye & Mahjoob, 2020; Darwish, Shaaban, Marsillac, & Mahmood, 2019; Mahmoud, 2020).

Globalization is generally agreed to reflect the highest degree of output significance,[56]. The construction industry faces numerous challenges in today's global market, such as economic developments , new markets emerging in the global economy, rising competition, the effects of technology, new and growing demands from suppliers , customers and society, and the need to maintain a highly qualified workforce at all levels (Bereznoy, 2019; Li, Greenwood, & Kasseem, 2019). In order to increase productivity, quality and production, global competition is pushing construction organizations to reconsider their construction [59]. The construction industry in Iraq must compete by continuous product development, more value-added processes, and product quality improvement to meet the challenges of the 21st century [52]. As Bataineh (2018) concluded, the real source of CAIS is efficiency, and the advantage of CAIS will lead to high results. In this scenario, Iraqi construction companies would lose their competitive edge in the local and foreign markets, with low productivity and efficiency.

Generally, the role of CAIS, organizational culture, and company size in achieving the high-performance concentration businesses of contracting companies are accepted. In the modern and global age , companies began to initiate a need to concentrate on managing computerization as a performance and organizational asset (Jyoti, 2017 Jamkhaneh, 2018) as well as a source of wealth[60] with the growing importance of computerization. The importance of success circumstances through strategic cultural growth for CAIS has been stressed by many researchers (Ali, 2019 Tallon, 2019).

In general, the degree of CAIS adoption in Iraq is moderate, and this may be because CAIS is still in an evolving phase [61]. Although, due to its role in the success of the company, CAIS is important for the construction sector (Bataineh, 2018). In the Iraqi context, CAIS activities may be considered relatively recent, as most organizations are at the early stage of the formal implementation of CAIS [62]. Therefore, the extent of CA practice in Iraqi construction companies is still in its infancy stage. (Douifi, 2018)

Iraqi construction organizations must keep up with the dynamic needs of the sector in order to make effective use of CAIS [64]. Iraqi construction organizations need to be mindful of the obstacles that may impede the progress of CAIS initiatives when implementing the CAIS strategy. The key challenge lies in recognizing people-related variables where the most challenging factors to change are behaviors and habits [65]. The improvement of quality and efficiency by putting great emphasis on professionalism, creativity, and computerization in the effort to improve the quality of life, according to Abed (2018) (Hendiani and Bagherpour 2019). The government and the Iraqi Ministry of Planning have made several efforts to increase the level of computing and skills among the construction players to achieve the objective. As part of the construction industry, the management of computerization in construction companies would enable the government to achieve its goals.

In investigating the antecedent factors to CAIS and/or Constrictions companies' performance previous studies investigated the effect between several factors like technology contact, organization contact or environment contact with the performance(Ahmed & Kasseem, 2018; Clohessy & Acton, 2019; Knabke & Olbrich, 2018; Niknejad, Hussin, & Amiri, 2019), None investigated the effect of organization culture as a mediate effect between CAIS factors (technology, organization, and environment) and construction companies performance, as well as the effect of firm size as moderator effect between organization culture and construction companies performance, has not been investigated. Most of the previous studies, especially in developing countries, examined the organizational culture as an independent variable and they argue the need to examine this factor as a mediation effect as well as the size of the company as a moderator Moreover, it has been reported that professionals recognize greater dependence on human capital in the Iraqi construction industry, although technological innovation is said to be a minor supporting aspect for improving efficiency(Al-Baldawi, 2019).

Therefore, recognizing the need to concentrate on the management of CAIS for construction undertakings in Iraq, this study seeks to explore the CAIS program involving the organizational culture and scale of the construction undertakings in Iraq as a holistic approach, as one of the solutions to the problems facing construction undertakings in Iraq. With such deliberations, it is expected that Iraqi construction companies will boost their success in the global market.

The problem statement can be summarized as the need for a unifiedimplementation framework that presents a holistic prescription of the factors that should be considered for CAIS and construction companies .This is, then, further addressed from two fronts: First, the potential value of CAIS in construction companiesand how its adoption and implementation in construction sector can help in drivingthe national economy. Second, thelimitations of previous related studies and why investigating the antecedent factors andtheir respective constituent elements would address the limitations.

Conclusion

The construction company has potential benefits from harnessing the strengths and functionalities of CAIS and applying the analytics of its performance. However, there are some risks and issues that need to be considered when implementing CAIS and performance in construction company. Implementation and implementation of CAIS and Efficiency will lead to significant changes in the field of development constraints and its competitive space. Such modifications may create opportunities or may be new threats to the domain. The ability of CAIS and Efficiency was addressed in this study to provide a clear understanding of the deployment of intelligent construction and to identify the factors that may influence implementation. The technique to be used is also illustrated. The aim of this study is to investigate the potential of CAIS and Performance within construction companies and to analyze the existing CAIS and Performance uses of the intelligent construction system in Iraq. The investigation is done to determine if the implementation of CAIS and the output of construction companies should be of great benefit to the government. Our research findings will be used to propose a CAIS structure, organizational culture, and success in construction companies.

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